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The 2 Feedback Loop Axiom and its Implications for OR, Systems Thinking and Wicked Problems in Planning and Crime Prevention

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SIMPLE system

- ▶ SIMPLE system – few elements, few links, maximum 1 feedback loop.

COMPLICATED system

- COMPLICATED system – many elements, many links, maximum 1 feedback loop

COMPLEX system

- Any number of elements and links, 2 or more feedback loops.

Obesity treatment
causal loop model

COMPLEX system

- Any number of elements and links, 2 or more feedback loops.

Definition:

Human cognitive limit of understanding

- When a person can not correctly predict the outcomes of a situation.
- Beyond that point it is no longer useful to ask a person about a situation. Their answers will be false, mistaken, deluded or second-hand.

2 Feedback Loop Limit Axiom

- There is at least one human cognitive limit of understanding systems.
- People cannot correctly predict the outcomes of systems involving two or more feedback loops, or two or more linked system archetypes.
- At the same time, individuals can be fully self-convinced that they have correctly understood the system although their understanding and prediction of outcomes are demonstrably incorrect.

Implications of 2 Feedback Loop Axiom

- Qualitative data gathered from people about the behaviour of a complex system is intrinsically faulty
- Data gathered from stakeholder groups is similarly intrinsically faulty

Consequences 2 Feedback Loop Axiom for Systems Thinking

- ▶ The 2 Feedback Loop Axiom points to problems with validity of :
 - ▶ Soft systems methodology
 - ▶ System dynamics methods
 - ▶ Critical systems heuristics and similar systems methods
 - ▶ Hybrid systems methods
 - ▶ Beer's VSM (levels 3, 4 and 5)
 - ▶ Stakeholder consultations on wicked problems
 - ▶ Etc...

Limitations – Operations Research

2 feedback loop for addressing wicked problems

- Gather pictures of views from all stakeholder/expert perspectives
- Identify key elements and relationships between them from each different stakeholder/expert source.